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D1.3 - Roadmap of future hardware and long-term development plan for each pilot application

WP1: Software Scalability & Usability

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Executive Summary

Future hardware development will have a significant impact on all areas of scientific computing including the Life Sciences. Upcoming extreme-scale compute platforms will offer great opportunities for tackling important, large-scale scientific questions. In this document we analyze from the viewpoint of biomolecular applications the requirements for different Exascale aspects such as HPC architectures, software management, programming environments, I/O and storage etc. We discuss the near-term hardware developments in processors, network, and memory and I/O in the light of these requirements and we explain the impact that they will have on the core applications. Our findings are already well publicized among the European HPC stakeholders via several working groups which are involved in the development of the ETP4HPC Strategic Research Agenda and the PRACE Scientific Case, as well as the EXDCI (<http://exdci.eu>) project in which BioExcel is leading the Life Science working group.

Bio-molecular simulation scientists require effective and usable simulation software that runs well on the hardware resources they can access now. The development of these codes must also target the likely directions of future hardware that we have learned from leading vendors and development consortia. This will ensure that the investment in Exascale-era technologies will deliver the expected benefits of improved bio-molecular simulations. These include supporting the design of new drugs, obtaining better understanding of biochemical pathways, and opening new doors for further innovation. This deliverable gives an overview of what we currently see as potential directions and then implementation plans for each of the pilot codes that will suit those directions.

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1 Introduction

A key focus for BioExcel is on the development of bio-molecular simulation software that has the feature set, documentation, reliability, scaling, and performance to meet the needs of its user community over the long term. Its users need the ability to run large workflows on the Exascale, and also to be able to use their departmental clusters and personal laptops to do a wide variety of simulation science. That software necessarily runs on real hardware that has both procurement and running costs, and so the software should be designed to use all of those kinds of hardware efficiently. This directly improves the ability of end users with a fixed budget to resolve a scientific question quicker, or answer more questions, or answer broader questions.

High-performance computing hardware has been changing rapidly for many years, often leading the trends found more broadly elsewhere in the technology sector. The quest for Exascale performance is currently a key driver of innovation. In earlier decades, as manufacturing processes improved to permit making smaller components, processor clock speeds increased with each generation of hardware, permitting application developers to come to expect performance improvements merely from buying new hardware. However, since the mid-1990s, clock frequencies have been essentially constant, because of the prohibitive amount of heat generated at higher frequencies. Instead, all semiconductor manufacturers have shifted to strategies that apply the higher transistor density into increasing the number of compute units. These trends have led to the need for application developers to need to perform arithmetic in tandem across multiple identical compute units, with multiple threads of execution distributed across multiple processor cores, and perhaps also hardware designed for the individual application. This requires major investment in the software, to expose parallelism in the existing algorithms, to discover and test new paradigms, and to then deploy code that executes correctly, while ensuring the correctness and thus scientific quality of the results. It is likely that the Exascale era will bring even more and new disruptive changes to the hardware arena, requiring care and attention from the software developers.

The software developed and maintained within BioExcel shares a number of these concerns. It is critically important that the limited resources available are used only to develop software that will be portable to new architectures, and the changes to compilers, libraries, runtime systems and operating systems that will come alongside them. The purpose of this document is to report the expectations of the BioExcel software developers on current and future hardware trends, observe relevant risks, and sketch how best we can take advantage of the new opportunities that will come. Two considerations of hardware-driven software complexity are paramount:

- It needs to be hidden from the end user of the application, who are often scientific experts, but neither programmers nor computing specialists.
- Application developers need to design modular software that provides for both high-level hardware-agnostic logic, and low-level routines that extract best performance.

We begin in section 2 with discussing the general requirements of bio-molecular software, continue in section 3 with the trends in hardware expected by members of the BioExcel project, describe co-design and Extreme Scale Demonstrator developments in section 4, and finish in section 5 with a long-term development plan for each BioExcel pilot application. Many of the plans are driven by scientific needs, but where applicable the needs of adapting to hardware changes will be made clear. It should be noted that some BioExcel software developers have current non-disclosure agreements with multiple hardware vendors, which are honored in publishing this document.

2 Requirements of biomolecular software

Achieving Exascale execution of commonly used algorithms for biomolecular modelling and simulations imposes a range of requirements for future hardware systems and associated software stacks. We have summarized some of the most important aspects in Table 1. The presented results of the analysis have been shared with EXDCI (<http://exdci.eu>) and published in the EXDCI deliverable “D3.1 - First set of recommendations and reports toward applications”, in section 2.4.4 of which we have given an overview of the common requirements and recommendations regarding the challenges faced by Life Science software.

Table 1. Exascale aspects of biomolecular software.

Exascale aspects	Requirements
HPC System Architectures and Components	large width vector units, low-latency networks; high-bandwidth memory; fast transfer rates between CPUs<->accelerators; heterogeneous acceleration, floating-point
System Software and Management	dynamic (task) scheduling, support for adaptive scheduling of workflows
Programming Environments	standardization, portability, task parallelism, fast code driven by e.g. Python interfaces, implementations accessible also at sub-Exascale levels
Energy and resiliency	distributed computing techniques to handle resiliency/fault tolerance
Balance Compute, I/O and Storage Performance	post-processing on the fly, data-focused workflows, handling lots of small files in bioinformatics
Big Data and HPC Usage Models	proximity of data generation and analysis/visualization resources, workflows, machine learning for analyzing simulation data, high-throughput sampling, efficient HPC and HTC job scheduling
Mathematics and Algorithms for extreme scale HPC systems	multi-scale algorithms, task-parallel algorithms, electrostatics solvers, ensemble sampling & clustering theory, ensemble simulations

2.1 HPC system architectures and components

Some of the fundamental algorithms for biomolecular modeling require frequent updates of the data, which is being shared among compute units during parallel execution. This includes also the data shared with accelerators, the latter being well utilized by existing codes e.g. GROMACS.

Thus, in order to achieve Exascale capabilities, future HPC systems need to support low-latency communication by providing fast networks and fast transfer rates between the main CPU and the accelerators. Large-width vector units and heterogeneous acceleration will also have a significant impact on minimize compute time.

2.2 System software and management

It is currently unrealistic to expect in any computational field that a single job will be able to execute simultaneously billions of e.g. MPI processes without suffering major performance degradation. At the same time, important scientific questions could be addressed by using a number of applications that are connected in larger workflows. Thus, future systems will need to provide appropriate support for workflow execution and dynamic task scheduling for orchestrating them.

2.3 Programming environments

Over the years there's been a reduction in the types of HPC hardware with several vendors abandoning custom processors and moving to x86 compatible architectures. Still, the proliferation of accelerators and upcoming hybrid systems puts again strain on the software developers to ensure compatibility and efficient usage of the systems. Standardization of programming environments will greatly help to improve the portability of codes and minimize the effort to do so. Given the heterogeneous nature of the hardware and the complexity of algorithms to be implemented, application developers expect that Exascale systems ought to come with a mature programming stack that supports out-of-the-box task parallelism and interfaces for fast code development, but are also aware that usability of hardware via mature support in standard software components generally takes time to mature.

2.4 Energy and resiliency

Future Exascale systems will obviously have very big energy requirements. Light-weight/low-power processors will be major players in those architectures and applications will have to support them. The sheer number of active components during a typical Exascale run will naturally increase the chances of hardware faults. Distributed techniques for handling such faults and providing necessary resilience of the systems will be of crucial importance. Until fully automated generic managers are in place, the applications will need to provide an acceptable way for checkpoints and restarts of simulations in anticipation of potential system faults.

2.5 Balance compute, I/O and storage performance

Extreme-scale simulation runs of cellular systems or screening of active compounds in drug design generate massive amounts of raw data, from which valuable insights need to be extracted. Moving raw data between compute and storage nodes will be highly inefficient. On-the-fly techniques for pre-/post-processing need to be integrated in data-focused workflows for optimal system utilization and faster time to solution.

2.6 Big Data and HPC usage models

The above aspects are closely linked to the Big Data and HPC usage models in biomolecular research. High-throughput sampling and machine learning are becoming fundamental for the area. Thus, comes the importance for proximity of data generation resources and the analysis/visualization (where necessary) ones.

2.7 Mathematics and Algorithms for extreme scale HPC systems

The complexity of soft matter systems (in particular the biomolecular ones) necessitates the improvement of multi-scale algorithms for their modelling. Exascale-level simulations will demand highly efficient electrostatic solvers for appropriate treatment of near- and long-range interactions. The solvers along with compute kernels for other types of interactions need to be handled by task-parallel algorithms for optimal execution schemes. Ensemble simulations are also in major demand of task-parallel frameworks for orchestration of sampling, clustering, data extraction etc.

3 Expected Future Hardware Developments

The quest for Exascale is putting severe requirements on hardware developments, most importantly on the overall power consumption of systems. The currently most power efficient system on the Green500 list (<https://www.top500.org/green500/lists/2016/11/>), an NVIDIA owned system with NVIDIA P100 Tesla GPUs achieves 9.5 GFLOPS per Watt; scaling this system to the Exascale would draw over 100 MW. The original Exascale studies¹ suggested to cap the power draw at 20 MW to make the system manageable and affordable. This means a further 5-times improvements in the GFLOPS/W ratio would be needed. Although it currently seems that a power draw over 20 MW would be acceptable for first Exascale systems, the overall goal is still to achieve more than 50 GFLOPS/W.

In order to achieve this goal, advances on all levels of hardware are needed. Below we summarize the most important trends in processor, memory, and interconnection technologies and discuss their impact on biomolecular applications.

¹ Bergman Keren et al. " Exascale Computing Study: Technology Challenges in Achieving Exascale Systems Peter Kogge, Editor & Study Lead (2008)", <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.165.6676&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

3.1 Processors

With the end of Dennard-scaling increasing computational power in CPUs is achieved through exploiting explicit parallelism. This primarily happens through an increased core-count and larger SIMD/SIMT (vector)-units. Current architectural trends see two main incarnations of CPUs: systems with relatively large cores and advanced optimization techniques like pipelining, multi-level caches, and vector units and systems with many small, simple cores. The former includes “standard”, “heavy-weight” CPUs like Intel Xeon, Sparc, or Power, while the latter includes “light-weight” systems such as GPUs (like NVIDIA’s Tesla) and many-core systems, like Intel’s Xeon Phi/MIC architecture. In addition, systems originally developed for mobile devices, like ARM, gain traction on the HPC market as they started to provide techniques known from “standard” CPUs like pipelining, multi-level caches, and vector-units. FPGAs are also being considered for HPC, albeit not as seriously as ARM, yet.

Projections of current processor and CMOS technologies suggest that neither heavy- nor light-weight systems would be able to achieve the Exascale power consumption goals, but only hybrid systems combining both technologies. These systems will have a few, very powerful cores for tasks that do not exhibit massive parallelism, and many light-weight cores for massively parallel tasks; potentially FPGAs will also be included in the packaging. First examples pointing in this direction are hybrid NVIDIA/Power and NVIDIA/ARM systems; a potential convergence of Intel’s x86 and Phi/MIC developments points in the same direction. While this integration of heavy- and light-weight cores will make interaction and data transfer among them much easier, applications (or higher level programming environments) will still have to manage this heterogeneity, making the choice of programming model a prime concern. Biomolecular simulation software needs to plan to port all key implementations to run on accelerator architectures by the time Exascale machines will be commonly available. This effort will deliver benefits in pre-Exascale times, and at sub-Exascale levels, so is a top priority.

BioExcel is, primarily through the joint partners KTH, EPCC, and BSC, engaging with recent and ongoing efforts on Exascale programming models like EPiGRAM² and INTERTwINE³. It is widely accepted that probably no single programming model will lead to the Exascale. Research in this area made potentially useful information to BioExcel developers, particularly from EPiGRAM’s efforts on MPI, PGAS, and hybrid memory programming as well as INTERTwINE’s efforts on programming model interoperability. Feedback to their developers was also provided, in that free and open-source software dependent on public funding cannot adopt a new hard dependency on compilers, libraries, or runtimes that are not freely available.

In the case of biomolecular applications, hybrid hardware architectures will be of critical importance for solving scientific problems that require Exascale compute

² Epigram project: <http://www.epigram-project.eu/>

³ Intertwine project: <http://www.intertwine-project.eu/>

capabilities. The reason being that many of the fundamental algorithms that are used in the domain fit well into streaming architectures (e.g. solving N-body interactions of particles). Efficient exploitation of this complementarity would clearly open the path to solving scientific challenges at the extreme scale.

3.2 Memory and I/O

High Bandwidth Memory (HBM) and Hybrid Cube Memory (HCM) are new technologies aimed at drastically improving the bandwidth between the main memory and the CPU. They exploit Die Stacked Memory (DSM), where DRAM is placed as close as possible to the processing elements. This either happens through placing the memory on the same die as the processing element or on separate wafers connected with through-silicon via (TSV) technology. The former gives a higher bandwidth and lower latency but requires a design freeze earlier in the process, as the whole chip must be laid out as a single part. The latter allows for design changes to a single layer but has a (comparatively) lower bandwidth and higher latency, as communication still occurs as if between chips (as it technically is), although with an improved speed compared to that of current CPU to DRAM.

HBM and HCM are two currently competing interfaces for such Die Stacked Memory. The first system providing HBM, is the most recent Intel Xeon Phi (*"Knights Landing"*) with up to 400GB/s⁴. Further bandwidth improvements are scheduled to be released with the next generation of Intel's Xeon Phi (*"Knights Hill"*).

We expect significant benefits from this improved bandwidth for biomolecular applications, in particular when dealing with accelerators (GPUs) and any latency in data transfer rates will have a significant impact on the performance of the codes. Some applications (like MD), whose memory requirements fit into the L3 or even L2 cache will benefit less. How to efficiently use the deeper memory hierarchy and who (operating system, runtime system, application layer) is still an open issue that will need to be resolved. Application designers need support for new hardware to be provided in middleware (including back ends of compilers, libraries and runtime systems), because they cannot invest heavily in non-portable code that supports emerging technologies that may not prove useful or widely available.

Apart from these much-improved memory technologies, we also see a convergence of memory and storage through storage class memory, providing additional layers in the memory hierarchies. These layers will typically be provided by NVRAM technologies and although NVRAM latency is still orders of magnitude higher than standard DRAM technology, it improves access to large amounts of data significantly, which can be very beneficial for in-memory

⁴ <http://wccfttech.com/intel-knights-landing-detailed-16-gb-highbandwidth-ondie-memory-384-gb-ddr4-system-memory-support-8-billion-transistors/>

databases, data analytics, whole system persistency, checkpointing, or application databases. Burst buffers based on SSD technology, providing essentially I/O caches and checkpointing facilities, are already widely used in new HPC systems. With improving technologies, the usage models will be largely enhanced. A use-case particularly important for biomolecular applications is efficient data sharing among different applications in an ensemble or workflow, where for example multiple meaningfully different simulations can start from an almost identical input data set. This pattern, common to many biomolecular applications, will be much improved through this technology, paving the path towards Exascale ensemble computing applications. One examples is the NextGen-I/O project [www.nextgenio.eu], which explores the possibilities of this new memory technology. BioExcel may access these new technologies via the joint partners EPCC and BSC once viable prototypes exist, which could permit us to explore the impact of this technology for biomolecular applications.

New storage technologies, like for instance developed in the SAGE project (<http://www.sagestorage.eu/>)⁵ further complement the I/O subsystem. The SAGE system is built on multiple tiers of storage device hardware technology. This will typically include at least one NVRAM tier (e.g. Intel 3DxPoint technology, at least one flash tier and at least one disk tier. This multi-level storage subsystem will also include its own compute capabilities, allowing to move computations previously done on the compute nodes to the storage subsystem. This includes e.g. pre- and post-processing of data as well as data transformations in workflows.

Biomolecular applications will particularly benefit from pre- and post-processing of trajectories closer to the storage as well as dynamically changing simulations based on-the-fly analysis of the results of the previous time step. This will require application developers to refactor their code to understand the capabilities of multiple kinds of I/O environments, once the form of such APIs becomes clear, and then tailor the behavior at run time to make efficient use of what is available. However, until such systems are likely to be in the hands of bio-molecular simulation scientists, the impact from such code development effort will be quite low.

These new technologies will have a significant impact for the pre-/post-processing capabilities of biomolecular codes. More and more important scientific questions are data driven and rely on the analysis of large amounts of raw data. Free energy studies via molecular dynamics simulations, biomolecular recognition for drug screening, macromolecular formation and reactions, studies of dynamic pathways such ion transport, protein/DNA/saccharides/ligand interactions etc. are some of the cases in which data is being generated computationally. Enabling on the fly pre-/post-processing via efficient workflows and executing them as close to the storage system as possible will considerably improve the time to solution. Similarly, “wet-lab” experiments such as cryo-EM also rely on the fast processing of massive amounts of imaging data, which ideally should be done as close to the source as possible.

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<http://sagestorage.eu/sites/default/files/Sage%20White%20Paper%20v1.0.pdf>

Even though it is currently difficult to predict the nature of the impact of the upcoming I/O layers, this space should be watched since it could provide significant opportunities if libraries are transparent or provide standardized APIs that can be used easily in biomolecular applications.

3.3 Network

The current generation of high-performance networking technologies offers a link bandwidth of 100 Gb/s and near-term future generations are planned to increase this to 200 and 400 Gb/s. Within this generational framework, several promising network technologies focusing on low-latency ($< 1 \mu\text{s}$) required by many HPC-applications follow an evolutionary path building on proven existing concepts, while some start-up companies attempt to build on more disruptive, yet highly promising technologies that so far need to demonstrate their usefulness in large-scale systems.

Mellanox is leading the bandwidth race with the announcement of 200 Gb/s HDR Infiniband in November 2016 as a direct successor to the existing 100 Gb/s EDR Infiniband⁶. Intel offers the Omni-Path technology, currently at 100 Gb/s, which is based on both QLogic's Infiniband and Cray's Aries technology⁷. Perhaps the biggest promise of the Omni-Path architecture is the announcement of integration of NICs with Intel's high-performance processors starting with the Xeon Phi Knights-Landing product already available. The Bull Exascale Interconnect (BXI) developed by Atos is another interesting contender that takes elements from both Ethernet for the physical layer and Infiniband for the management. The most striking feature may be the adoption of the Portals 4 API developed by Sandia National Laboratories as the interface towards the network hardware⁸. Extoll, a spin-off from the University of Heidelberg, is a German start-up offering a more disruptive technology with its current Tourmalet ASIC providing yet another 100 Gb/s low-latency option⁹. A notable feature is the ability of the NIC to act as a host to allow accelerators like GPUs or early Intel Xeon Phi Knights Corner processors to be directly attached to the network, a feature that was used in the booster design of the European DEEP research project (<http://www.deep-project.eu>). Finally, Data Vortex Technologies takes disruption a step further

⁶ Brad Smith, "Mellanox Launches 200Gb/s HDC InfiniBand AOC and DAC LinkX[®] Cables," in *Mellanox Blog*, November 29, 2016, accessed April 5, 2017. <https://www.mellanox.com/blog/2016/11/mellanox-launches-200gbs-hdr-infiniband-aoc-and-dac-linkx-cables/>

⁷ M. S. Birrittella et al., "Enabling Scalable High-Performance Systems with the Intel Omni-Path Architecture," in *IEEE Micro*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 38-47, July-Aug. 2016. doi: 10.1109/MM.2016.58

⁸ S. Derradji, T. Palfer-Sollier, J. P. Panziera, A. Poudes and F. W. Atos, "The BXI Interconnect Architecture," 2015 IEEE 23rd Annual Symposium on High-Performance Interconnects, Santa Clara, CA, 2015, pp. 18-25. doi: 10.1109/HOTI.2015.15

⁹ Extoll GmbH, Tourmalet The HPC Network ASIC, 2016, accessed April 5 2017. http://extoll.de/images/pdf/Leporello_Tourmalet_2016.pdf

focusing primarily on small messages with their technology built around “congestion-free” switching of 128-bit long messages in the buffer-less Data Vortex switch¹⁰.

While there seems to be a clear roadmap towards increased bandwidth, latency and small message performance seem to be lagging behind, requiring larger messages to utilize the available bandwidth. The BioExcel applications need to keep this in mind as a design constraint, but it is equally important that future hardware design and investments are guided by the needs of the programs that justify the investments. It favors strategies that reduce the need for all-to-all communication, and makes clear that there will be strict limits imposed by network hardware capabilities on the number of nodes upon which a latency-bound implementation can run. Fast-multipole electrostatics in GROMACS may prove more effective than PME at the Exascale (BioExcel work actively pursued in WP1), assuming that the trade-off between speed and accuracy can be effectively resolved. It also makes clear that a single molecular dynamics simulation of a million MPI ranks is unlikely to be able to be implemented efficiently. Thus the strategy should target algorithms that couple large numbers of simulations together in workflows that adaptively direct sampling work into regions that should have it, rather than brute-force ensembles of millions of simulations.

Another long-going debate is what tasks should be executed by the network devices (NICs and switches) and what best to leave to the more general purpose processors in the system. Here the Omni-Path architecture is leaning more towards “on-loading” or leaving more work to the application or system processor side of the system, whereas Mellanox and Atos try to offload more chores to the network, including some form of application specific processors into the network. The critical point here is to what extent applications can make use of the off-load capabilities offered by a network and to what extent intermediate libraries like MPI are adopted to do so. In extreme cases, as already demonstrated in the financial industry, parts of the application may be implemented embedded into the network, a strategy that may require careful planning and analysis of the costs and benefits. Another interesting trend is the ability access resources on remote nodes. Such resources might include memory, accelerators or storage, without the intervention of any of the nodes processors, with Extoll perhaps offering the most advanced capabilities in this respect. For applications, this could permit checkpoint data to be pushed to remote nodes for safekeeping without impacting the perhaps totally unrelated computations on the active node.

Another area of active development is the attachment of the NIC to the rest of the system, with on-package or on-die integration certainly opening up new possibilities for tight integration with for instance the processor’s memory system and caches¹¹. However, even discrete NICs may profit from taking part in the

¹⁰ Data Vortex Technologies Website, accessed April 5, 2017.

<http://www.datavortex.com/performance>

¹¹ Ajima Y. et al. “Tofu Interconnect 2: System-on-Chip Integration of High-Performance Interconnect,” in: Kunkel J.M., Ludwig T., Meuer H.W. (eds)

cache-coherency protocol, for instance via the CAPI protocol as already announced by Mellanox. This may be especially important when considering small message performance, since non-coherent I/O protocols like PCI-Express are usually optimized for bulk-transfer bandwidth.

In conclusion, it is likely that applications will see a steady increase in network bandwidth, yet more and more care will be necessary to actually be able to utilize the speed offered by next generation network technologies. This may require careful placement of data-structures in memory and utilizing multiple NICs in a node to release pressure on the intra-node interconnect; accessing network functionality from a sufficient number of threads to compensate for network latency; and reformulating algorithms to take advantage of the off-loading and in-network capabilities for instance by using non-blocking composite network operations like collectives.

3.4 Deductions from upcoming Petascale-era machines

Several conclusions can be drawn already from Petascale era machines. The upcoming “Summit” supercomputer, to be sited at the US Oak Ridge National Laboratory in 2018 will be built based on IBM’s Power9 CPU technology and NVIDIA’s Volta GPUs. The total system is expected to deliver around 200 PFLOP per second, which is still rather short of the Exascale. It is expected to have around 4,600 nodes, which is many fewer than its predecessor Titan, which had 18,688. Each node will deliver in excess of 40 TFLOP per second, principally from its projected six Volta-generation GPUs.

A typical GPU-accelerated bio-molecular simulation using GROMACS 2016 might have 200,000 particles, while supercomputing usage can involve systems 10-100x larger. The short-ranged non-bonded interactions are evaluated for each particle interacting with around 600 possible neighbors (for a cutoff of 1.0 nm), and consume around 200 flop each. So, a lower bound for the amount of short-ranged computational work is 24 GFLOP per MD step for the smallest systems we target. Additional work for long-ranged PME work and bonded interactions occupies the CPU. Pascal-era GPUs permit GROMACS to take sub-millisecond steps, so if we assume such a GROMACS simulation on Sierra can take 2,000 steps per second, the total flop requirement is 48 TFLOP per second. This is comparable with the peak output of a single node, and peak flop output cannot be expected from the smallest molecular dynamics systems we target. The current implementation only uses the GPU during the computation of forces, which necessarily wastes some of its value. Moving the computation of forces for other interaction types to the GPU, along with the update calculations will make noteworthy improvements in efficiency and throughput by the time GROMACS 2018 is released, so long as effective use can be made of the intra-GPU NVLINK network that Summit will support. However, it seems unlikely that a single typical GROMACS simulation (in contrast to larger scaling showcase systems) will be able make use of more than a

handful of such nodes unless dramatic improvements in inter-node message-passing latency also occur. Such improvements are very difficult to deliver, and we have not seen such claims made.

The trend towards fewer nodes with greater capacity for floating-point operations is consistent across all planned pre-Exascale systems we have seen, so it is clear that Exascale strategy for such bio-molecular simulations cannot be based around using large numbers of nodes for single simulations. Five opportunities for simulating in the Exascale era on larger numbers of nodes have been identified:

- using workflows that couple multiple simulations to target the computational work to the regions of sampling space that need it,
- using implementations that scale to larger numbers of computational units, possibly including fast-multipole treatments of electrostatics,
- using larger systems that require more computational work per step, e.g. multi-million-particle materials-science simulations,
- using more realistic model physics, e.g. polarizable force fields, and
- addressing problems requiring more expensive model physics, e.g. enzyme reactions requiring QM/MM treatment.

Note that most of these possibilities do not apply to current-generation bio-molecular MD, where PME already works well, adding more atoms makes the ensemble more difficult to sample, and where polarization and/or QM treatments are not yet clearly required. Current bio-molecular simulations of systems not cherry-picked to show good scaling will only be usable at the Exascale with considerable investment in code quality while targeting new hardware, and only as part of workflows that couple multiple simulations together.

4 Co-Design and Extreme Scale Demonstrators

An important milestone towards European Exascale systems will be the Extreme Scale Demonstrators (ESDs), conceived by the ETP4HPC, that will showcase various technological trends and allow to assess their potential towards the Exascale in a realistic setting. *“The EsDs are complete hardware and software systems designed in a strong co-design relationship between technology providers and application providers, which can be used in a production-like mode. They should facilitate fast commercialisation of the architectures and technologies, and thus, become a basis to build European capability in Exascale.”*¹² BioExcel has been driving the application focus in the ESD discussions, coordinating input from all the CoEs through a series of workshops. The findings and requirements reported in this deliverable have also been made available to the core ESD group as proper co-design from the beginning will be mandatory for building usable systems. The developments of BioExcel software are expected to make them efficiently usable on these future platforms, if the overall system design takes the requirements developed for biomolecular software into account.

¹² ETP4HPC Recommendations for the WP18-20

While concrete actions towards ESDs will have to wait until first consortia are being formed, BioExcel partners have engaged in various co-design activities, both with individual vendors and larger consortia. Table 2 below gives an overview of these activities:

Table 2. Co-design activities between BioExcel partners and hardware vendors or consortia.

Partners/Project	Activities
KTH/NVIDIA	Fine tuning of CUDA kernels for GROMACS; improved build system support; curation of micro-benchmarks for correctness testing
KTH/Intel	Planning for development of OpenCL interfaces in GROMACS for support of future streaming architectures;
KTH/Intel	Fine tuning of GROMACS for Intel's Knights Landing
KTH/Intel	Acceleration of RELION on Broadwell, Skylake and Knights Landing
KTH/FZJ/MPG SPPEXA project and KTH/Tokyo Tech	Design and testing of fast-multipole method implementations in GROMACS
EPCC/CRESTA project (http://cresta-project.eu)	EPCC led CRESTA, one of the first three Exascale projects, which focussed on software challenged at the Exascale using a software co-design approach. One of its six key applications was GROMACS.
EPCC/NextGenIO project (http://www.nextgenio.eu/)	EPCC is currently leading the NEXTGenIO hardware co-design project which is developing a new HPC system based on Intel's next generation Xeon processor and their revolutionary 3D XPoint non-volatile memory technology which promises up to 6TB of NVRAM in DIMM form for each processor socket. Both HPC hardware and software, particularly focussed on data scheduling, are being developed to exploit this revolutionary new memory technology.
BSC/MontBlanc project (http://www.montblanc-project.eu)	MontBlanc is developing an Exascale architecture based on ARM processors; exploring different alternatives for the compute node

	from low-power mobile sockets to special-purpose high-end ARM chips.
Juelich, BSC/ DEEP-ER project (http://www.deep-er.eu)	<p>DEEP-ER is building a prototype based on the second generation Intel® Xeon Phi processor, a uniform high-speed interconnect across Cluster and Booster, non-volatile memory on the compute nodes, and network attached memory providing high-speed shared storage; optimising a selection of HPC applications for that system.</p> <p>The project runs bi-weekly inter-workpackage meetings where interdisciplinary design and development topics are discussed. Workshops with application developers are also regularly organized.</p>
KTH, Juelich/ Sage Storage Project (http://www.sagestorage.eu)	SAGE improves the performance of data I/O and enable computation and analysis to be performed more locally to data wherever it resides in the architecture, drastically minimising data movements between compute and data storage infrastructures. With a seamless view of data throughout the platform, incorporating multiple tiers of storage from memory to disk to long-term archive, it enables API's and programming models to easily use such a platform to efficiently utilize the most appropriate data analytics techniques suited to the problem space.

BioExcel regularly monitors the output of hardware-software co-design projects targeting Exascale application deployment. EU-supported projects such as NextGenIO, MontBlanc, DEEP-ER, and Sage are designing and building prototype hardware and software. Similar efforts are underway in the US, China, and Japan. Our observations as application designers of these projects are that we should plan to depend on standard languages, compilers, runtimes, and libraries. We expect that new hardware will, wherever possible, support those, because it is not sustainable for multiple applications to port to custom infrastructure whose lifetime is uncertain. For example, new low-latency network hardware needs to come supported by modules that make them work in readily available MPI or PGAS libraries, rather than expect application designers that already support MPI to write a layer that functions like MPI. Similarly, while power consumption is a key design constraint for future Exascale machines, application designers can only

take advantage of the capabilities of the hardware to the extent that a callable API exists, or that libraries like hwloc will accurately report on it. For example, GROMACS has almost no need of the memory provided on typical HPC systems. However, there is no API that permits a GROMACS simulation to instruct the operating system to turn off memory that is not required in order to save power.

5 Long-term development plans for the applications

As mentioned in the introduction, the BioExcel application codes both consider the likely path of future hardware in their long-term planning and define the needs of the applications that should help guide future hardware development investments. Both the BioExcel codes and most other proven-impact scientific applications have solved this by choosing languages such as C/C++/Fortran and Python that have very large user communities and outstanding track record of portability. For programs such as GROMACS (where simulations are intended to be suitable for Exascale deployment) there are also a number of architecture-specific language extensions and libraries used. Additionally, scientific users need the simulation software to be both highly usable and highly adaptable, which drives the plan to make BioExcel software available via both command-line applications and workflows using API/web interfaces.

Public support for work on free and open-source software infrastructure is essential for making progress for usability and impact at the Exascale, and the BioExcel applications have been selected based on their proven impact track record. The pilot codes represent a selection with very different degrees of parallelization maturity, not to mention completely different challenges for parallelization as well as development QA. The strategy followed in the project is to help each of these user communities improve towards Exascale, but on their terms. For the selected applications, the BioExcel effort has particularly focused on improving support for new architectures, scaling, usability and sustainability in terms of better code documentation and testing, and gradually helping the broader communities involved in these codes to move to more modern development standards (which is not easy given the code size and scientific requirements). In addition to work directly funded by BioExcel, the project has also taken far-ranging responsibility for integrating development efforts as well as identifying future development needs for the applications where additional support will be required (i.e., beyond BioExcel).

5.1 Long term development plan for GROMACS

GROMACS is a mature project that has a core development team at KTH in Stockholm, and numerous regular external contributors. In early 2017, there were five full-time developers, five regular part-time developers, and numerous occasional contributors. BioExcel funds only a small part of the team, but for the first time this has enabled more professional project management including processes for both internal QA and external collaborations, not to mention a plan for required future work where BioExcel is able to coordinate and steer a much larger number of developers and contributions from outside of BioExcel.

A large number of important directions for future development have been identified. These are listed here, but are not ordered into a formal timeline. In practice, the requirements of other available funding resources will shift, and rarely can any developer focus solely on one or a few tasks in order to deliver it by a predictable time, given that the feature often depends on several others and the team spends an increasing part of their time on QA. The skill set of available developers often determines which targets can receive most effort. Progress is also contingent upon the availability of resources for testing, and since GROMACS has moved to full formal code review, it also requires time for the review of the code by other expert developers. It should be noted that GROMACS does not only target bio-molecular simulations, and the software is increasingly being used in other areas. For the first time, several of the targets reflect the needs of e.g. materials science simulations. Finally, as part of BioExcel and the mission of supporting all types of simulations for the community, the GROMACS project has started much closer collaborations (in particular for training) with Amber & NAMD, which are the other two major codes in the field, and these new collaborations are likely to influence future development of all codes.

5.1.1 Modularization of core mdrun simulation functionality

One of the key requirements to achieve a flexible code that can be driven by other programs to deploy workflows on the Exascale is to make the core routines modular and testable with modern QA strategies. It is also necessary to create the flexibility to deploy to future hardware features and architectures with minimal disruption to the code base while making it easy to see that implementations are correct and maintainable. This work will port hundreds of thousands of lines of C89-style code to C++11, including use of RAII-style resource management, Doxygen developer documentation and unit testing coverage for old code. Several fundamental changes are required, including robust error handling that does not simply terminate the program, relaxing assumptions that all available hardware can and should be used, and that hardware will not fail over the lifetime of the simulation. This work is closely related to the new specifications of software engineering, testing and QA previously reported in BioExcel D1.1, and covers all tasks reported below.

5.1.2 Evolution of Exascale-suitable task parallelism

The main challenge for molecular dynamics simulations to be relevant for Exascale deployment is to improve strong scaling for the often relatively small systems used in concrete biomolecular applications. While GROMACS has a good performance and scaling reputation, improving this even further is constant high priority, in particular for BioExcel. The major workload of these simulations is the computation of forces, and this often requires the execution of several very large kernels, and numerous small kernels. The latter will generally not parallelize over large numbers of cores because the overheads of preparing to run the calculation take an amount of time comparable with the execution time of the kernel. The problem is even more challenging when multiple computing units (GPUs, sockets of CPUs, nodes) have to coordinate work, because units need to do local work when that is all that is available, but be prepared to react to data from other computing units as soon as it becomes available. As we approach the Exascale, the number of computing units that need to be used will grow rapidly. Continuing to

improve strong scaling that functions on a wide variety of hardware architectures and configurations will require a kind of adaptive scheduling that requires a task graph, rather than a pipeline of kernels that are assumed to be able to be spread over all available resources when it is time for each to be run. This will require a complete overhaul of the entire execution back end of GROMACS, which is supported by numerous of the code modernization and modularization activities mentioned here.

5.1.3 Deployment and acceleration for new architectures

GROMACS has a strong track record of portability, and with the new modular CPU-side SIMD support layer recently developed (in combination with extensive automated unit test frameworks) it is close to trivial to port to new architectures. This layer decouples the CPU kernels from the low-level infrastructure that implements the required memory and arithmetic operations, and the code also has a very general nonbonded kernel architecture that is easy to adjust for different hardware profiles. In GROMACS 2017, we will deploy acceleration for AMD's new Ryzen and Naples CPU platforms, as well as tuning for Intel's Skylake-EP AVX512 chips. As new flavours of Intel, AMD, ARM and Power chips emerge and seem relevant for high-performance computation, hardware-specific acceleration support for all these architectures will be added.

5.1.4 Moving more algorithms to accelerators – PME on GPUs

The short-range interactions in GROMACS are already being executed on accelerators such as GPUs, but as the performance gap between accelerators and CPUs is constantly increasing there is a need to move more parts of the execution to accelerators. Work is underway to port the long-range electrostatics interactions (particle-mesh Ewald, PME) code to run on GPUs, and early phases of this work may appear in GROMACS 2017. Further work to generalize to a wider range of devices and degrees of parallelism, and to automatize task assignment between different compute units, will follow in GROMACS 2018. Progress here is a key stage in the evolution of GROMACS to support the expected accelerator-heavy Exascale-era compute nodes described above.

5.1.5 Enable Accelerator/GPU-only simulations

While some future hardware will be balanced between CPUs and accelerators, we also expect a number of systems to be entirely accelerator-focused. To provide good performance for this hardware, it would be beneficial with a version of the code that executes almost exclusively on GPUs with a subset of functionality (this would require porting the integration, constraints, and bonded interaction code to GPUs). Depending on the Exascale hardware development, there could also be machines where accelerators/GPUs are paired with low-performance CPUs, and then the software would benefit from eliminating time-consuming data movement between compute units, and improve energy efficiency, and also permit simulations to run faster on less costly hardware. It is expected that the cost-efficiency of performance increases on GPUs and accelerators is likely to continue to outstrip those for CPUs, and is a key requirement for molecular dynamics to function well at the Exascale where accelerators will likely deliver most of the flops. This plan is very dependent on future hardware development, and based on announcements over the next year we might deliver early implementations targeting high-throughput usage on single nodes in GROMACS 2018/2019.

5.1.6 Deployment to new accelerator architectures

GROMACS currently supports devices that run NVIDIA's proprietary GPU acceleration language CUDA, and the industry standard vendor-neutral OpenCL language (on both AMD and NVIDIA devices). It is likely that any new accelerator will likely support either of these languages, and the main effort to support these would be to make minor adjustments to how the work is structured and mapped to execution units. It is possible that some Intel devices will be useful enough to support with OpenCL in the future. There is also interest in making GROMACS able to run on a GPU-based fully free software stack, which should facilitate interactions with and optimization for new custom Exascale hardware developed e.g. in the Exascale demonstrator projects.

5.1.7 Support for fast multipole electrostatics for better scaling

Methods like particle-mesh Ewald have been the *de facto* standard for treating electrostatics in MD simulations the past decades. The main advantages are high sequential performance due to the use of FFTs and that they are relatively simple to implement. But the 3D-FFT is ill suited for high parallelization because of the four 3D-grid transposes required per MD time step. Both strong and weak scaling of MD simulations is limited by the latency and overhead of the all-to-all MPI communication. The fast multipole method (FMM) provides better formal scaling as $O(\#particles)$ both for computation and communication (unlike $N(\log)N$ for FFT methods). However, standard FMM have been too slow to be usable in practice, and there are issues with energy conservation, which we have recently found a solution for. The GROMACS team is collaborating with groups at the Juelich computing centre and Tokyo Tech to adapt FFM methods for MD and integrate them into GROMACS. This will provide both better strong and weak scaling, with very large impact in the high-scaling regime. Furthermore, since FMM is by default non-periodic this enables exact electrostatics for Exascale simulations of flow which often use ten to hundreds of millions of particles.

5.1.8 New C++11 templated short-ranged kernel implementation, and support for tabulated interactions for both CPU and GPU architectures

To consolidate the GPU and CPU code paths, the next stage in the evolution of the hundreds of flavours of GROMACS high-performance short-ranged kernels is to move away from bug-prone preprocessor-based code generation and instead use C++11 extern templates. This will permit code analysis and debugging tools to work flawlessly, because conditionality can be implemented within the compiler, relying on it to eliminate code branches that will be dead at run time, and we will be able to provide full unit testing for any user-specified interaction form. After support for user-provided tabulated interactions is added, this will permit the removal of the deprecated group-style cutoff scheme, along with a great deal of supporting code, which will make it much easier to handle the transition to a modular library – and this in turn will enable us to expand the types of interactions and force fields supported. Many knowledge-based force fields, particularly in materials science, produce interaction functions that are not based on an easily-described mathematical formula. The potential and force for such interactions

must be looked up from tables for each particle pair. Such kernels need care because one must choose interpolation schemes that are able to run fast on the hardware, while providing a bounded error. In principle, different hardware (e.g. CPUs and GPUs) could suit different schemes because of differences in instruction and cache latencies, but all such should provide an equivalent and thoroughly tested implementation so that users do not need to be aware that the difference exists. To make use of such support, the topology description within GROMACS must be extended so that it is possible to choose tables for unique atom pairs, or pairs of all types, etc. This would significantly enhance the usability of GROMACS for non-traditional applications, including both materials science and special potentials currently only available on slow or non-scaling simulation codes.

5.1.9 Support for polarizable force fields

Traditional molecular mechanical force fields model the electrostatic behavior of particles by a single fixed partial charge, perhaps characteristic of a residue regardless of whether it is solvated or buried in an apolar environment. Accurate treatment of numerous simulation problems requires more flexible treatment. GROMACS has long supported the Drude oscillator polarization model, which was recently modified and extended. However, after implementing the new generation of nonbonded kernels, it will be possible to expand the interactions supported by the code to also cover more advanced force fields, which will be important to improve the quality of results e.g. in drug design and free energy calculations.

5.1.10 Implement long-term stable C++ and Python library APIs

A central theme for modern scientific codes is that users increasingly want to compose modules, or even call a program as a library from another. Users need the ability to design and test simulation and sampling algorithms without being developers, and they also need to be able to manipulate the resulting output in automated fashion. For the future, we want to make both the modularized core mdrun library and all other tools available behind APIs that are intended for long-term stable support and to work intuitively both in C++11 and Python 3. Some initial work is currently done in collaboration with US GROMACS developers, with additional funding by NIH grant R01-GM115790-01A1. However, providing good APIs for the entire library will require much larger effort, but it will make it significantly easier to use the code in advanced scripts. The impact is expected to be very high, since it will allow a wide range of other codes to directly use the fast GROMACS simulation engine – one example is that it could enable BioExcel to use GROMACS as the modeling engine inside HADDOCK in the future.

5.1.11 Updated and improved sampling algorithms for free energy calculations

While strong-scaling efforts provide one path to Exascale execution (which we are already pursuing for GROMACS in BioExcel), it will not be possible to efficiently parallelize a single MD simulation on hundreds of thousands of particles over millions of processing units. Supporting coupled sets of simulations is a key part of the GROMACS Exascale strategy. Numerous special-purpose algorithms are already implemented, including replica-exchange, extended-ensemble, umbrella sampling, free-energy perturbation, the adaptive weight histogram method, and computational electrophysiology. These require test suites and code updates to provide better tools for simulations that use computing resources more efficiently. We are working towards Exascale-era simulations using advanced sampling

algorithms, such as Markov state models, milestone, the string method with swarms of trajectories, and not least adaptive free-energy sampling. These will be implemented by an adaptive workflow engine that manages thousands of independent simulations within a high-performance environment. The Copernicus workflow system (<http://copernicus-computing.org/>) developed alongside GROMACS, and other similar systems, have proved this concept, however it will not be feasible to tolerate the overheads of job scheduling and file-based I/O at the Exascale. An MPI-aware server-client binary is most likely to work best, so that the available work and hardware are matched to run efficiently, even as the required work changes and perhaps the hardware environment changes as hardware fails or other jobs monopolize computing or network resources. Other alternatives, such as in-memory file systems may be an option, but to achieve the throughput needed for Exascale, simulations will require a much tighter integration between workflow, scheduler, I/O, and the simulation engine compared to what is available today.

5.1.12 Enable more advanced automated simulation workflows of BioExcel tools

The combination of the Copernicus workflow engine, a stable Python API, and advanced sampling algorithms will make it possible to automatically combine and integrate tools such as the STaGE engine for automatic parameterization of molecules, and the PMX topology generator developed as part of BioExcel. This will enable users to deploy fully automated workflows in a high-level language that can compute quantitative relative free energies of binding of families of ligands to families of proteins. Such workflows should be highly adaptable, both to use the hardware efficiently despite heterogeneity or run-time failure, and to recognize how to sample efficiently in each particular sub-problem.

5.1.13 Modernization and modularization of simulation preparation tools

In addition to the core simulation engine and sampling algorithm libraries, GROMACS also packages numerous tools suitable for preparing simulation topologies and conformations that would be extremely valuable if they were available as a modern modular library. In particular, it would have large impact if all these tools had modern error-handling and user interfaces with simple data structures that could be accessed both from C++11 and Python, although this will require substantial focused efforts.

5.1.14 Expansion and modernization of trajectory-analysis tool suite

GROMACS has long enjoyed popularity among users for its fully-featured set of 50+ tools for producing scientific insight from raw simulation output. However, many of the tools combine features that were developed by different people and do not work correctly in combination, or have less tested implementations contributed by individuals focused on science and collaboration, rather than proven-quality software with good unit test coverage. An extensible and parallelizable framework for implementing tools has been partly designed, however many of the analysis tools are still using old and bug-prone implementations. To improve the experience of GROMACS users, we should greatly expand the test coverage, remove duplicate and broken features, and port to the new framework. This will further permit those modules to be deployed behind the API work, which in turn will facilitate collaborations with other codes and usage in workflows.

5.1.15 Modular integration framework

Molecular dynamics proceeds by integrating the equations of motion. Forces on particles are computed based on the positions of all particles, those forces are used to update their velocities, after finally the velocities used to update the positions. Numerous alternatives are available, and can have subtle strengths and weaknesses. It is important for the bio-molecular simulation field to be able to assess these alternatives on real-world problems, which requires that the time-consuming force calculation are provided by a high-performance package. The current GROMACS implementations of integrators require considerable clean up and improvement before this is possible, but it is something we are planning to address on the medium term. Such modularization will also be needed in order to support a GPU-only mdrun execution path. This work is underway, with additional support by the NIH grant R01-GM115790-01A1.

5.1.16 Molecular dynamics applied to flow

As technological and biomedical flow application move down to the micro- and nano-scale, the molecular nature of liquids becomes more apparent. In recent years, that has seen a strong increase in the use of large-scale MD simulations of flow to study molecular aspects. But although what is called the nano-scale is small, it is still very large on the MD scale with systems from millions to hundreds of millions of atoms. Unlike typical biomolecular applications, which have fixed size, these flow simulations are even a relevant target for single-machine Exascale supercomputers. The main issue here is that this is not simple weak scaling. As the system size increases, the time scales also increase. Thus, there is still the strong need to minimize wall-clock time per step by using more cores. To achieve this, the same parallelization strategies as for bio-molecular simulations are required (overlapping calculation and communication and a better tasking model). In particular, the optimization and integration of the fast multipole method for electrostatics is important to significantly push up the scaling limit.

5.1.17 Flexible input format

Historically, GROMACS defined its own plain text key-value input file, implementing its own parser and requiring users to understand how to use it. This was a good decision when it was made, but now that standard formats and libraries for handling structured text input files exist, we plan to transition to using these. This will eliminate many kinds of possible bugs in the code, and support the modularization efforts elsewhere. Users will be able to edit the structured files in a syntax-aware editor of their choice. Developers extending the functionality of GROMACS will be able to make changes only in their new module, and not in multiple parts of the code.

5.1.18 Driving simulations from external inputs

Numerous new experimental techniques provide exciting opportunities for simulations that inform experiment, and vice-versa. The new flexible input format will support such efforts by allowing mdrun to access offline data sets that could be very large, so that the simulation can be driven by advanced Bayesian sampling algorithms into the regions consistent with the experimental data. Work on cryo-EM refinement is already underway supported by the Carl Trygger Foundation, and we see large potential in extending this to other sources of experimental or bioinformatics data.

5.1.19 Expanded implementation of trajectory and energy file formats

Existing enhanced sampling algorithms in GROMACS write output to a variety of custom output files that will be entirely unsuitable to run at the Exascale. Even existing algorithms impose the burden on users of coordinating dozens to thousands of output files. GROMACS currently supports the TNG next-generation trajectory format (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/jcc.23495>), which provides best-in-field compression of containerized molecular simulation data. All kinds of mdrun output need to be written to TNG, and analysis tools updated to use the new format. This will greatly improve usability of the tools, and the reliability of the knowledge generated with GROMACS.

5.1.20 Container-based deployment

Users will be able to use GROMACS effectively on cloud-based resources when a container can be obtained from a repository that will recognize the hardware and run an appropriately configured pre-compiled version of GROMACS. For some families of architectures, such as x86, this could be achieved via dynamic loading of shared libraries that match the hardware, but this approach is limited to hardware capable of running the same executable. For more heterogeneous situations, a dispatch algorithm is required.

5.1.21 Container-based continuous integration testing

The wide range of hardware, build configurations, and simulation algorithms supported by GROMACS requires rigorous automated testing. Portability is a key requirement for success during the transition to the Exascale, because it is not known what compilers, architectures and technologies will prove to be successful. This can only be assured through testing. However, maintenance of dozens of test machines is too time-consuming. We plan to replace these with container-based test environments that automate build and deployment via a script. These can be used to maintain a much wider range of test environments without needing to manually log into machines to maintain software versions. A fully automated benchmark suite would also be possible to deploy in this framework.

5.2 Long term development plan for HADDOCK

We started the development of the new version of HADDOCK3.0 that will bundle a list of new features both at the CNS core and front-end levels. This new release will include in the standalone version pre-processing and validation steps that are currently only handled by the web server.

Together with this major update, we also started the complete rewriting of the web portal and server to replace a local custom library (Spyder), developed by a former lab member. This Spyder layer is currently performing the first validation in the server workflow before calling the Python layer. The web server will now rely on the Flask framework (<http://flask.pocoo.org/>), successfully used for two recent web portals, DisVis and PowerFit. This new version of HADDOCK, considering its importance, have been integrated within the attached roadmap, extended here.

5.2.1 Complete rewrite of the HADDOCK webserver

Our first objective, highlighted at the top of the roadmap, is to finish the rewriting of the HADDOCK web server. This transition involves porting all current features of HADDOCK2.2 web server in Flask together with the integration of new ones, in particular the support for cryo-EM restraints and coarse grain models, which will be introduced with HADDOCK3.0. Due to the complexity of the web server, which currently provides 7 interfaces to run a docking simulation with different level of control over the parameters (up to 500 exposed to users at the most advanced level) and different input data, we are organizing the development of the web server in a bottom-up manner where independent and simple tasks are progressively implemented, linked and extended. An overview of the first developments made for HADDOCK3.0 on Flask are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - New HADDOCK3.0 submission form interface

5.2.2 Building current web server pre- and post-processing stages into the HADDOCK workflow

In the current setup, the HADDOCK web portal handles a number of pre- and post-processing steps independently from the HADDOCK workflow managed at the Python level. This is the main difference between running a local version of HADDOCK and submitting jobs via the server interface. An overview of the current

web server workflow is shown in Figure 2 and the detailed workflow handled by the main HADDOCK Python level in Figure 3.

Figure 2 – HADDOCK web portal workflow. The left panels describe the pre-processing part of the workflow, the central panel refer to the internal HADDOCK workflow (see Figure 2b) and its job submission machinery, and the right panel describes the post-processing workflow.

Figure 3 – HADDOCK internal workflow.

The current local install of HADDOCK only performs the internal workflow. All pre- and post-processing steps have to be done by the user manually.

The second step of our planned development will see the progressive integration of the web server pre- and post-processing steps into the main HADDOCK workflow. This will greatly benefit users using a local version of HADDOCK, but will also be key for reaching Exascale interactome modelling (see below). The downside of this for a local installing means that more third party software (some with licenses) must be available / installed (e.g. molprobit for structure pre-processing and PRODRG for generating ligands topologies and parameters). A possible solution to this problem would be to only perform limited pre-processing on the web portal, save the resulting files and then start the HADDOCK3.0 workflow, either via the web portal using the resources we are providing, or off-loading the computations to local HPC resources.

This implies a redesign of the system of communication (between the web server and the workflow) in order to reflect the new framework lying under the web server.

5.2.3 Improved, interactive visualization and analysis of results

The current results pages of the server present the results of the post-processing steps in a static manner. The new Flask framework will enable a new set of post-processing steps and will allow us to extend the online visual interpretation and analyses of HADDOCK results. For this purpose, we will create a database system for the storage of HADDOCK output. This database will be queried by Python modules to make the bridge with advanced JavaScript solutions on the client side. We aim to provide a complete and interactive Visual Analytics solution to the users that will let them directly interpret HADDOCK results within their web browser and then reduce the amount of time and the amount of data that have to be processed as of today.

5.2.4 Benchmarking and release of HADDOCK3.0

Once the integration of the web server and the workflow will be done, each feature of HADDOCK will be independently tested and benchmarked. We have already developed a complete suite of test cases to assess HADDOCK at each feature and bug-fixing implementation. This automated benchmark allows us to monitor any deviation in the data output by HADDOCK for different sets of application (protein/protein, protein/DNA, protein/RNA, multi-body docking, etc.). Proper benchmarking however requires running a full docking protocol to check the consistency of the results, something which will remain CPU intensive.

The official version 3.0 will be released, together with a complete documentation wrapping up all new features and modalities of usage. In parallel, the web server will be ported to Docker containers and Virtual Machines to make use of cloud or local resources during particular events e.g. workshops, courses or workflows involving HADDOCK.

5.2.5 Toward Exascale interactome modelling with HADDOCK

Reaching Exascale, which will be required for large scale simulation of interactomes (e.g. the human interactome is currently estimated to consist of several 100,000 interactions, which are modulated by all kind of post-translation modifications will require efficient workflows and submission machinery. This is also true on the context of large scale drug screening for example.

In the current setup, the HADDOCK internal workflow (Figure 3 above) would run typically on a master node with computations within the workflow sent as individual jobs to a local batch system or grid/cloud HTC resources using DIRAC (see the central panel in Figure 2 above). Such a setup will clearly not scale up in a HPC setup where tens of thousands of docking runs would be started simultaneously, each generating thousands of individual jobs sent to the batch system.

A possible solution to this would be to directly send the complete workflow to the batch systems and then, once nodes have been allocated, run the workflow and all its associated computing within the node in some kind of multithreading setup. In the scenario of interactome modelling or large scale drug screening, this would mean sending tens of thousands or more of those workflows directly to the batch system (instead of millions of individual jobs as would be the case in the current setup), which will clearly generate much less load of batch system itself. In order to do this, we intend to redesign the internal job handling machinery. While the compute intensive parts of the HADDOCK workflow are embarrassingly parallel (green boxes in Figure 3), the pre- and post-processing steps are more sequential in nature, with, in particular, some of the post-processing being quite I/O demanding. New developments in storage technology like NVRAM and storage-attached compute capabilities could help with pre- and post-processing and data exchange.

5.2.6 HADDOCK-GROMACS workflow

As one of the BioExcel project Use Case (UC5), we started the development of a workflow involving two BioExcel flagship software, HADDOCK and GROMACS. This workflow will allow using GROMACS both upstream and downstream of HADDOCK, either to sample input models for docking with HADDOCK or to refine, rescore or test the stability of the docked models generated by HADDOCK.

The first step in this direction consists of choosing the optimal workflow system to bridge the two software (a work also related to WP2). We decided to team up with the group of Dr. Daan Geerke, professor of Computational Medicinal Chemistry and Toxicology at the VU University (Amsterdam, NL). A senior research scientist from his group works on a new WAMP workflow (Web Application Messaging Protocol) integrating GROMACS, with support of the Dutch e-Science center. We agreed on the design of the workflow and identified the different components that need to be developed on both side to get it work. In parallel, a complete benchmark of protein/protein complexes has been assembled to test this workflow.

As a consequence, we defined a 3-steps plan:

- 1) Finalization of the workflow prototype on VU side with an extension of its capabilities to handle HADDOCK's input/output requirements. On the UU side, development of a Python interface to HADDOCK via its XMLRPC API. This interface should allow any Python pipeline to remotely access HADDOCK methods exposed via its API. It is also aiming to extend usual features offered through the web server to tightly control the process.
- 2) Testing phase during which the workflow will be used to process our assembled benchmark. We foresee putative extension of the workflow features during this period as well as debugging sessions if needed.
- 3) Finally, we aim to release the workflow during the first quarter of 2018 and publish it in parallel. We plan to write several tutorials that make use of the workflow and organize workshops under BioExcel branding, associating head developers of HADDOCK and GROMACS.

This workflow engine will also contribute to reaching Exascale for interactome modelling as explained in the previous section.

5.3 Long term development plan for QM/MM with CPMD and GROMACS

At the end of the BioExcel project, we will end up with a new HPC efficient QM/MM interface (MiMiC) coupling CPMD with GROMACS. Some key directions for future development have been identified and reported below.

5.3.1 Coupling to other MM codes

The interface has been implemented with a high degree of abstraction, having in mind the possibility to interface CPMD also with other classical molecular dynamics (MM) codes by minimal code intervention. For this reason, a natural medium/long term plan is to establish collaborations with the developers of the

other commonly used biological oriented MM codes (e.g. NAMD (<http://www.ks.uiuc.edu/Research/namd>), AMBER (<http://ambermd.org>) and Desmond (https://www.deshawresearch.com/resources_desmond.html) in order to develop in this codes the required layer that allows them to communicate with the interface and through that with CPMD, as we are currently doing together with the GROMACS development team. This work should be facilitated by the new BioExcel-initiated collaborations between the codes. In this way, we would provide a quite general QM/MM interface of CPMD that can work virtually with any classical force field. This agility is a key attribute for effective function of QM/MM at the Exascale, where users might have lots of special reasons (not least personal preferences) for using a specific QM or MM code.

5.3.2 Polarizable MM codes

Within the funded period, we are going to make the new QM/MM interface compatible with force fields adopting atomic multipole-based electrostatics with explicit dipole polarizability. It is therefore quite natural to think to extend the list of the supported MM codes to molecular modeling software that uses polarizable atomic multiple force fields like AMOEBA¹³. Short-term this could be provided by TINKER (<https://dasher.wustl.edu/tinker/>), and long-term it would interface to the GROMACS work described in section 5.1.9.

5.3.3 Multiple time steps

Another long-term plan is to enable the QM/MM interface to work with the multiple time step approach. Multiple time-scale algorithms exploit the natural separation of time-scales in chemical systems to greatly accelerate the efficiency of molecular dynamics simulations. The usefulness of these methods in systems where the interactions are described by empirical potential is well known¹⁴. At the same time, recent advances in this direction have allowed overcoming the difficulties associated with splitting the potential for a quantum system into fast and slowly varying components, bringing to multiple time step integrators in *ab initio* molecular dynamics¹⁵. This permits computational speedups of 4-5x compared to standard quantum *ab initio* schemes. Currently, there are no multiple time step algorithms implemented in CPMD. In addition, the extension of these approaches to the QM/MM framework is expected to enable one to get similar speedups but for much larger systems such as the biological ones. A useful collaboration with the GROMACS development of multiple time step integration algorithms may emerge in the future.

5.3.4 Time-dependent density functional theory

Time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT) is a quantum mechanical approach employed to solve the time-independent nonrelativistic electronic Schrödinger equation (SE) and consequently to investigate the properties and dynamics of many-body systems in the presence of time-dependent potentials, such as electric or magnetic fields. The effect of such fields on biological systems

¹³ Y. Shi, Z. Xia, J. Zhang, R. Best, C. Wu, J. W. Ponder, P. Ren, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **9**(9), 4046 (2013)

¹⁴ H. Grubmüller, H. Heller, A. Windemuth, and K. Schulten, *Mol. Sim.*, **6**, 121 (1991)

¹⁵ N. Luehr, T. E. Markland, T. J. Martinez, *J. Chem. Phys.* **140**, 084116 (2014)

can be studied with TDDFT to extract features like excitation energies, frequency-dependent response properties, and photoabsorption spectra. TDDFT is one of the less computational demanding techniques enabling the calculations of optical properties, and therefore it is one of the most widely used approach to investigate optical properties of biological systems. Of course, the algorithmic complexity of such problems still requires HPC computational resources to be solved. CPMD implements TDDFT. However, the new QM/MM interface currently does not allow extending the application of TDDFT to hybrid QM/MM resolutions. Therefore, another long-term plan of the developer team of the QM/MM interface is to enable the interface to support TDDFT calculations.

5.3.5 Machine learning models and towards Exascale

The above-mentioned numerical intrinsic complexity in finding experimentally accurate solutions to SE limits the possibility to perform routine electronic structure calculations and high throughput screening.

When Exascale resources become available, the combination of efficient QM/MM interfaces developed here, and parallel enhanced sampling techniques would give us the possibility to perform *ab initio* ligand screening, i.e. virtual screening based on accurate first-principle free energy calculations and not simply on predictions based on generic chemical properties from large libraries of compounds. Parallel enhanced sampling techniques that allow speeding up the free energy reconstruction by exploiting almost embarrassingly parallel schemes are already available, such as the multiple walker metadynamics method implemented in CPMD. However, the major bottleneck for reaching a form of “high throughput screening” based on QM/MM simulations is still the quantum part.

It has been shown that the task of repetitiously solving the SE can be mapped onto a computationally efficient, data-driven supervised machine learning (ML) problem instead¹⁶. In these models, expectation values of quantum-mechanical operators are inferred in the subset of chemical space spanned by a set of reference molecular graphs, enabling a speedup of several orders of magnitude for predicting relevant molecular properties such as enthalpies, polarizabilities, and electronic excitations¹⁷. QM reference calculations provide training examples. After training, accurate property predictions for new as of yet unseen molecules can be obtained at the base cost of the underlying ML model, provided that the new query molecule lies close to the space spanned by the reference data. So far, this technique has been only applied to small molecular systems treated fully quantum mechanically. On a medium/long term period, we plan to implement the required machinery in the interface in order to enable the ML-based QM/MM calculations for larger biologically relevant systems as well.

¹⁶ R. Ramakrishnan, P. O. Dral, M. Rupp, O. A. von Lilienfeld, O., *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **11**, 2087–2096 (2015)

¹⁷ K. Hansen, F. Biegler, R. Ramakrishnan, W. Pronobis, O. A. von Lilienfeld, K-R. Muller, A. Tkatchenko, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **6**, 2326–2331 (2015)/ R. Ramakrishnan, M. Hartmann, E. Tapavicza, O. A. von Lilienfeld, *J. Chem. Phys.* **143**, 084111 (2015)

5.4 Long term development plan for PMX

The hybrid structure/topology generation for simulations of alchemical transformations of ligands is planned for the year 2017, quarters 2 to 4. The treatment of arbitrary ligands poses a challenge more difficult than handling amino and nucleic acids. For the latter cases the diversity of the chemical libraries is low and the structure sets are well defined, thus mutation libraries were pre-generated and made available to the community. In contrast, every ligand mutation is unique and needs a separate treatment.

Firstly, prior to building a hybrid ligand structure/topology, an atom mapping needs to be established for the two compounds. A number of routes exists to establish a desired mapping. One way is to rely on a graph based common substructure search to identify the morphable atoms, while the rest of the atoms ought to remain dummies. Another approach utilizes the Euclidean distance to map the atoms. This method, however, requires an alignment of the structures with arbitrary numbers of atoms. Our aim is to automate these mapping procedures and incorporate them into a single tool in the pmx package.

Having obtained an optimal atom mapping, the actual hybrid structures and topologies need to be generated. For that we are aiming to utilize the already developed pmx routines and extend them to the more general use to handle the ligand alchemical morphs.

The final step in the ligand treatment outlined for the year 2017 is generation of the optimal ligand maps for investigating large chemical libraries. Based on the aforementioned atom mappings between the ligands, the similarity between the compounds can be quantified. This enables usage of the graph-based approaches to identify optimal paths to connect ligand pairs to fully explore the library of compounds of interest.

In parallel to the ligand structure/topology handling, in 2017 we are planning to establish a set of tests for the amino and nucleic acid mutation libraries, as well as the ligand hybrid structure/topologies. Currently, all the consistency checks have been performed using an in-house software toolkit. We are aiming to bring this software to the level where it can be easily and robustly applied by the user to ensure the validity of a newly generated mutation library or a hybrid structure/topology. In addition to the testing software we plan to incorporate a set of short simulation protocols into pmx to check for the validity of the free energy calculations.

The pmx webserver has been successfully deployed in the first quarter of 2017 (Figure 4). Currently it provides automated support for the amino acid hybrid structure/topology generation in 5 contemporary molecular mechanics force fields. This provides the possibility to run alchemical free energy calculations on amino acid mutations without the need to install the pmx software and therefore takes an important step in rendering complex biomolecular simulations accessible to non-specialist users. In 2018 we are planning to extend the web features by incorporating nucleic acid mutations in DNA, as well as alchemical ligand

mutations. The latter provide a thorough means to perform lead optimization schemes based on accurate free energy based affinity estimates. This enables pharmaceutical workflows in academia as well as pharma industry to integrate high-quality *in silico* thermodynamic predictions and thus minimize the effort in synthetic chemistry and in vitro screening.

Figure 4 pmx webserver main page

In the long term, starting in 2018, we are planning to proceed with a tight PMX integration into the GROMACS package. To make this possible, we first need a stable Python environment as part of the GROMACS tools, as mentioned in the GROMACS plan, but this work is in the pipeline. The Copernicus workflow management system has a basis to support free energy calculations utilizing the GROMACS molecular dynamics engine. Therefore, it presents an attractive opportunity to integrate the pmx hybrid structure/topology generation into a fully automated setup to carry out large scale amino acid, nucleic acid mutation and ligand modification scans. Due to its GROMACS integration, PMX calculations will directly benefit from performance, optimization and scaling developments in the GROMACS package, as well as its broad, highly optimized support on a wide range of platforms and accelerators.

The key to bring PMX free energy calculations to the Exascale is automation: a fully automated, unsupervised workflow is a prerequisite to carry out massive mutation and ligand screens necessary for protein design and drug development. In close collaboration between the KTH and MPG teams, the PMX/GROMACS integration will be set up to achieve just that: an environment to carry out

massively parallel alchemical free energy scans either in an HPC environment or in the cloud, in which only the list of end results is reported to the end user. All intermediate control, including error handling, convergence control to a user-set level, internal consistency assertion, analysis of raw data and translation to user-digestible, presentation-ready formats will all be carried out seamlessly on the fly. Such a setup would enable both academic and industrial end users, that do not need to be experts in biomolecular simulations, to operate highly complex workflows on massive mutation or ligand databases and thus make optimal use of future hardware generations for protein design as well as drug development.

6 Conclusions

In this report, we have presented the views of BioExcel's software developers on the requirements they have from HPC and HTC hardware and middleware in order that they can target Exascale workflows. Expected trends in the attributes of hardware have been identified, and lessons drawn for the design and implementation of the BioExcel pilot codes. Those have been integrated into long-term development plans suited to the particular context, scale and complexity of the pilot codes.

7 Annex

7.1 GROMACS Roadmap

